

Enhancing TeleRehabilitation in Balance Disorders Patients: A Comprehensive Clinical and Cost-Effective Decision Support System

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Introduction

Motor deficits have an effect on activities of daily living, with locomotion and balance being essential for independence [1]. Approaches based on artificial intelligence can support the selection of appropriate interventions and the adherence prediction. The TeleRehaB Decision Support System seeks to develop an AI-powered system for clinical and at-home treatment of individuals at risk of falling. The system prioritizes early integration and individualized pathways for individuals with balance disorders (PwBD) [2].

Materials and Methods

The TeleRehaB DSS aims to integrate AI in balance rehabilitation by merging wearables and IoT devices for remote patient monitoring management. The system utilizes retrospective data to evaluate prognostic factors, treatment effectiveness, outcomes, and side effects [3]. It tailors rehabilitation interventions by considering factors such as type, intensity, technology usage, and projected compliance, catering to patients with diverse risk profiles. It also provides personalized intervention planning and management, evaluating patients' tech-savviness and their adoption of new technologies. The automated remote monitoring feature allows real-time performance evaluation, with virtual physiotherapists providing feedback. These methods allow for personalized and data-driven rehabilitation interventions in a closed-loop coaching system (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The intelligent analytics functionality within the TeleRehaB DSS platform

Results & Discussion

The TeleRehaB DSS system represents a breakthrough in automated rehabilitation, providing a multifactorial balance, cognitive, and auditory training program with integrated motivational and physical activity components. The system reduces falls-related injury costs by 25% and visits to health clinics by 20%. It outperforms exercise programs and technology for older adults, increasing daily physical activity by 25% and promoting enhanced cognitive, mental, and social well-being through personalized intervention components, thereby enhancing users' overall quality of life.

Multifactorial interventions are crucial for preventing falls in older adults with comorbid medical conditions. Balance exercise physiotherapy is effective in vestibular mild cognitive impairment and stroke patients. However, access to specialized balance rehabilitation services is limited, and existing programs often lack a multisensory and cognitive component. Improving access to comprehensive balance rehabilitation is crucial, especially considering the challenges faced by an aging population.

References

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Keywords:

Balance disorders, personalised rehabilitation, decision support, IoT, patient management

Acknowledgments

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2021 research and innovation actions under grant agreement No 101057747, as part of the TeleRehaB DSS project.